

An analytical study of women's representation in Indian politics: Special reference to loksabha elections 1952-2019

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Abstract :-

Women's representation in India's Politics is an important metric to evaluate progress in bridging gender inequities in the nation. India has a female population of 66.29 crore and is the largest and one of the most resilient parliamentary democracies in the world. As the country completes 75 years of independence, this research paper gives a historical account of the progress in women's representation in Lok Sabha over the past decades. It compares women's parliamentary representation with their share in legislative positions at the lower levels. It notes that despite impressive increase in turnout of women voters in elections, opening up spaces for participation of women in electoral politics has been a slow process as a result of deep-rooted structural constraints. It argues that institutional transformation, coupled with socio-economic emancipation holds the key to increased participation by women in electoral politics.

Key Words :- Women's representation, Lok Sabha, Parliament, Election

Introduction :-

The global average for the share of women parliamentarians stood at 24.6%. The share of women legislators in the Lok Sabha is 14.39% as of June 2019. The 2019 general election saw 78 women elected to the lower house of Parliament for the first time since independence where only 22 women were present in the Lok Sabha. There is a decreased gap in voter turnout between men and women, a positive sign toward gender inclusivity in the political sphere. India has not had a single women's movement that challenged patriarchal and gender norms in the last two decades. Education and wealth have aided women in political participation. Studies suggest that more women have started to organise themselves into economic groups, and financial freedom has pushed them to be more politically active. India ranks 141st out of 191 nations in the representation of women in Parliament.

Research Methodology :-

1: Analytical Research Methodology.

2: Descriptive Research Methodology.

Analysis :-

In New Zealand, the percentage of women in the legislature recently surpassed 50%. The Inter-Parliamentary Union reports that New Zealand is one of 12 countries worldwide that can say that by 2022, at least 50% of their parliaments will be made up of women. New Zealand was the first country to grant women the right to vote in 1893. Cuba, Mexico, Nicaragua, Rwanda, and the United Arab Emirates are more countries. Around 26% of lawmakers worldwide are female.

The Indian Scenario of women in Parliament :-

Women representation in parliament and most state legislatures across the country is below 15 per cent with 19 of state assemblies having less than 10 per cent women lawmakers, according to a government data. The state legislatures which have more than 10 per cent women lawmakers are Bihar (10.70), Chhattisgarh (14.44), Haryana (10), Jharkhand (12.35), Punjab (11.11), Rajasthan (12), Uttarakhand (11.43), Uttar Pradesh (11.66), West Bengal (13.70) and Delhi (11.43). According to the data presented by Law and Justice Minister Kiren Rijiju in the Lok Sabha on December 9, 2022 Andhra Pradesh, Assam, Goa, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Kerala, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Odisha, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu and Telangana have less than 10 per cent women legislators. According to the data, the share of women MPs in Lok Sabha and Rajya Sabha stands at 14.94 per cent and 14.05 per cent, respectively. At the same time, the average number of women MLAs in assemblies across the nation accounts for only eight per cent.

Increase in Women MPs since the first Lok Sabha :-

The first Lok Sabha in 1951 had 22 women MPs. The current Lok Sabha has 66. In the span of 54 years and 16 Lok Sabha elections it amounts to a three-fold increase in the number of women MPs that made their way to the lower house of the parliament. From 5% in 1951, women MPs constitute 12.2% of the Lok Sabha today. The rise in numbers has been steady through the years, both in absolute numbers and percentages. The notable exceptions have been the dip in numbers during the 6th Lok Sabha in 1977, the 9th Lok Sabha in 1989 and most recently the 14th Lok Sabha in 2004. The

trends show a marked and steady increase from 1991 onwards to the present Lok Sabha. The 1991 figures show a jump from 5% in the previous Lok Sabha to 7% and the steady increase from thereon (except for 2004). It would be interesting to understand the factors for this watershed year and continuous rise and also the fall in numbers during 2004. The average representation of women MPs

(12.15%) is higher than the national average of women MLAs in state assemblies, which stands at a dismal 9%. While the numbers have increased over the years, the percentage of women that make up the Lok Sabha even today is not a figure to be proud of, especially when the ideal number should be at 33% at least. We still have a long way to go.

Year of Election	Number of Women Representatives	Percentage of Women Representatives (%)
1951	22	5
1957	22	5
1962	31	6
1967	20	6
1971	28	5
1977	10	4
1980	28	5
1984	43	8
1989	23	6
1991	30	7
1996	40	7
1998	43	8
1999	40	9
2004	45	8
2009	50	11
2014	66	12
2019	78	14

Source : Election Commission of India
Women contestants in elections to the Lok Sabha :-

Central to the question of women’s representation in Lok Sabha is the appetite for women to take the political plunge and jump into the fray along with and against male candidates, getting tickets from their respective parties to contest elections and finally winning the seats that they contest. While popular perception might be that few women are willing to or have taken the political plunge, number of women contestants tells an interesting story. Between 1957(the earliest data available) and 2015, the total number of women contestants has increased from 45 to 668. That is a whopping 15 fold increase in the number of women contesting. If we looked at the data for male contestants for the same years, the number has increased from 1474 to 7583, a five-fold increase. The 15 fold increase in women contestants indicates towards the growing appetite

for women to enter the political fray and willingness to be part of political decision-making.

Source : Election Commission of India
Success rate of Women Vs Men :-

The other interesting story from the numbers over the years emerges from the relative success rate of women contestants as opposed to the male contestants. Consistently the success rate of women has been higher over the years than men. Success rate is the number of winners against the total contestants in that category. Women have had a greater success rate than Men in every single election. In some years, the difference has been quite stark. In 1971, the success rate for men was 18%, whereas it was 34% for women, which is twice that of men. For the current Lok Sabha, the success rate was 6.4% for men and 9.3% for women. This could mean one of the two things: Either women had a greater chance of winning from the seats that they stood from or that tickets were

being given to women who had a greater chance of success. While numbers point towards a broad but important trend, it is fair not to be carried away by absolute conclusions, but to slice the data further and look at more granular data to establish causal relationships. While looking at women contestants currently, it would be fruitful to look at constituency

level granularity of data to understand the profiles of women being given tickets within the context of entrenched patriarchal systems. What is the percentage of women who win come from political families and already nurtured constituencies as opposed to self-made women politicians?

Source : Election Commission of India

The above argument notwithstanding, it is important to understand that the rising numbers of women is an encouraging sign to pave the way for greater political participation of women. With the rise of new parties that don't rely on political patronage of families, party systems and more importantly money and muscle power, greater number of women entering the political fray can only mean encouraging signs for decision making for a section that constitutes half the population. Now, if that were to be topped with a constitutional mandate to reserve 33% seats for women, then we are headed for more gender equal times. Else, it would be a case of two steps forward and one step backward!

Womens as voters :-

More and more women are exercising their right to vote in elections and this may be because of the Election Commission of India's (ECI) efforts and the reservation quota, say experts. In the 17th Lok Sabha elections, the number of women voters outnumbered men in 13 states, while this had happened in just 10 states in 2014. Earlier, these trends were visible only in India's northeastern and southern states and Union territories. But in the 2019 Lok Sabha Elections, northern states like Bihar and Uttarakhand also joined this league. This is not an easy achievement if one considers history. The 1962 Lok Sabha elections saw a gap 16.7 per cent between men and women voters and in 2014 this was reduced to just 1.5 per cent. In the last few

decades, there have been a number of schemes and programmes targeting women which include direct transfer which has led to awareness among women and made them participate more in selecting people's representatives.

Source : Election Commission of India

What causes the low representation, and why?

Gender stereotypes :-

The role of managing household activities has been traditionally assigned to women. Women should be encouraged to move outside their stereotypical roles and participate in the decision-making process of the country. Due to the unequal allocation of household care duties, women spend significantly more time than males caring for the home and children. In addition to putting in time and effort during pregnancy and childbirth, a woman must continue to do so until the child has to be taken care of by her parents.

Sexist attitudes :-

Women have historically been tasked with managing home chores. Women should be encouraged to step outside of their preconceived roles and take part in national decision-making. Politics is a competitive field, just like any other field. At the end of the day, they are also up against female politicians. Many politicians worry that if there is a woman's reservation, their seats might be alternately allocated for female candidates, denying them the opportunity to even run for office. Uneven distribution of family care responsibilities means that women spend far more time than men in home- and child-care. A woman not only has to give her time and effort at time of pregnancy and childbirth, but it continues till the child is dependent on parents for care.

Competition :-

Politics, like any other field, is a field of competition. At the end of the day, Women politicians are their competition as well. Many of the politicians fear that, in the case of women reservation, their seats can rotationally be reserved for women candidates, thus, making them lose any chance of even fighting from their seats.

Political education is lacking :-

Education affects women's social mobility. Formal education, such as that offered at educational institutions, fosters leadership chances and instills crucial leadership abilities. They are unaware of their basic and political rights since they do not comprehend politics. Education influences the social mobility of women. Formal education such as provided at educational institutions create opportunities for leadership, and impart leadership essential skills. Because of a lack of understanding of politics, they do not know about their basic and political rights.

Lack of Political Networks :-

The lack of openness in political decision-making and undemocratic internal processes pose a challenge for all newcomers, but particularly for women as they tend to lack insider knowledge or political networks. For all newcomers, but particularly for women since they frequently lack insider information or political networks, the lack of transparency in political decision-making and the undemocratic internal processes provide a problem.

Lack of Resources :-

Because of their low proportion in the inner political party structure of India, women fail to gather resources and support for nurturing their political constituencies. Women do not get adequate financial support from the political parties to contest the elections. Women in India struggle to gather money and support to grow their political constituencies because of their limited representation in the inner structures of the political parties. Political parties do not provide enough financial backing for women to run in elections. They must comply with the rules that are placed on them and carry the weight of society due to social conditioning. The number of female candidates who are considered and nominated for office is directly and indirectly influenced by public opinions, as well as how many of them actually win in a general election.

Social Conditioning :-

They have to accept the dictates imposed on them and bear the burden of society. Public attitudes not only determine how many female candidates win a general election but also directly and indirectly how many are considered and nominated for office.

Unfriendly Environment :-

Overall political parties' environment too is not women-friendly, they have to struggle hard and face multi-dimensional issues to create space for them in the party. There has been increasing violence in politics. A significant rise in criminalization, corruption, insecurity has driven women out of the political arena. In general, political parties do not provide a supportive environment for women. Women must fight hard and deal with a variety of challenges in order to have a place in the party. Politics has become more violent recently. Women are no longer active in politics due to a major increase in crime, corruption, and insecurity.

What actions is the government taking?

- 1: It suggests amending the Indian Constitution to reserve one-third of all seats in the Lok Sabha, the country's Lower House of Parliament, as well as in all state legislative bodies, for women.
- 2: Article 243D of the Constitution mandates that not less than one-third of the total number of seats to be filled by direct election and the

total number of offices of Panchayat chairpersons be reserved for women. This guarantees the participation of women in Panchayati Raj Institutions.

3. 3:The Committee on Empowerment of Women was established for the first time in 1997 during the 11th Lok Sabha of the Parliament with the goal of enhancing women's status. Regardless of their political inclinations, the Committee members are supposed to collaborate for the empowerment of women.
4. 4:Article 25 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which is binding on signatory states including India, says that “every citizen shall have the right and the opportunity, without any of the distinctions mentioned in article 2 and without unreasonable restrictions to vote and to be elected at genuine periodic elections
5. 5:In 2014, under the leadership of the then Speaker of the Lok Sabha, Meira Kumar, the Rules of Procedure of the Lok Sabha were made entirely gender neutral.
6. 6:Since then, each Lok Sabha Committee Head has been referred to as Chairperson in all documents. This initiative is proof that amending legal documents to make them inclusive for all genders is an attainable goal if there is a will.

Remedies to increase women's political representation :-

1. 1:The equal engagement of all segments of society in mainstream political action is urgently needed in a nation like India, hence suitable steps should be done to encourage it.
2. 2:The Women's Reservation Bill, which asks for reserving 33% of seats in Parliament and all state legislative assemblies for women, must be approved by all major parties.
3. 3:There is a pool of women who have served as sarpanches and members of municipal bodies for more than three decades and have expertise with local government.
4. 4:They are eager to participate more actively in state legislatures and Parliament.
5. 5:In order for the recognised political parties to continue to be recognised by the Election Commission as political parties, it is necessary to put into practise the ECI's proposal to make it mandatory for them to ensure that a minimum agreed-upon percentage of women vote in State Assembly and Parliamentary elections.
6. 6:Studies have shown that the gender quota introduced in local administration through the 73rd and 74th Amendment Acts has increased the presence of women and enabled them to enter mainstream politics.

7. 7:We should fulfil our obligation to ensure equality as guaranteed by Article 14 of the Constitution, which establishes the right to equality as a fundamental right. Article 46 imposes a duty on the state to protect weaker sections from social injustice and all forms of exploitation.
8. 8:The Women's Reservation Bill (2008) (108th amendment) has also been introduced in the national Parliament to reserve 33 per cent of the Lok Sabha seats for women.
9. 9:We cannot achieve social development with equity and justice without equal representation of women in Parliament, which is why the Women's Reservation Bill is the need of the hour.
10. 9:India is a signatory to the Convention for Elimination of Discrimination against Women. It obliges states to take appropriate measures to eliminate discrimination against women in political and public life and, in particular, to ensure that women are as eligible as men to contest elections to all public bodies.
11. 10:Status of Nordic countries When one looks at the Nordic countries with the most female parliamentarians, it is clear that their national policies are more inclusive and gender-sensitive as female politicians are more likely to prioritise gender equality, safety and security, elderly care, children's welfare, women's health care issues.

Conclusion :-

India should have an Election Commission-led effort to push for reservation for women in political parties. Reservation for women in political parties— a more viable option. Quotas for women in Parliament as envisaged in the Women's Reservation Bill. Awareness, education and role modelling that encourage women towards politics and wipe out Gender stereotypes which perceive women as weak representatives. Inclusive economic institutions and growth—both necessary for and dependent on social empowerment—require inclusive political institutions. Women's leadership and communication skills need to be enhanced by increasing female literacy especially in rural areas. They should be empowered in order to break socio-cultural barriers and improve their status in the society. India is yet to pass a bill introducing 33% reservation in Parliament for women. This experiment at the local level (PRI's and ULB's) has been very successful.

B.R. Ambedkar once said that “political power is the key to all social progress”. Ensuring proportional representation to women in parliament is seen by policy makers as a panacea to the issues surrounding women empowerment. Recognizing the significance of roles of women in decision making

process in the society is critical to strengthen women's agencies for building a progressive society with equality of opportunities among all citizens. Male politicians must take a lead role in challenging traditions which foster inequality and also unequivocally condemn the misogynistic language that their counterparts use when it comes to women. SDG goal 5 has a target – ‘Ensure women's full and active participation and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision making in political, economic, and public life’. It needs to be achieved with the collective efforts of the international community (SDG goal 17- Partnership for the goals). There is no one-size-fits-all solution to ensure gender equality in politics. But there is plenty that can and should be done to ensure that women's voices are heard.

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